

EDUCATION IS THE SPIRITUAL SUPPORT OF THE FAMILY

Djuraeva Perdegul Saidovna

Nauai region National center of training teachers in new methods, Acting associate professor of the department "Preschool, primary and special educational methods"

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8101001>

Abstract. *Our sacred books and values, the artistic heritage of our great thinkers, the family is the preserver of the continuity of every people and nation.*

Keywords: *family, value, history, tradition, care, child, upbringing, philosopher, heart, book.*

Introduction.

As we all know, our holy books and values, the legacy of great Eastern thinkers always call us to live with honest work, courage, generosity and humility, justice and kindness. Of course, the spirituality, history, unique customs and traditions of any nation or nation cannot be imagined without national values.

Research materials and methodology.

The wisdom of Eastern scholars, including Ibn Sina, Nizamulk's "Politics", Nasir Khysrav's "Saodatnama", "Roshnoyinoma", Yusuf Khos Hajib's "Kutadgu Bilig", Mahmud Kashgari's "Devonu Lugatit Turk", Ahmad Yugnaki's "Hibat ul-haqayq", The attention to child education is reflected in the works of Abu Rayhan Beruni, "Nightmare" by Kaikovus, "Mahbub ul-Qulub" by Alisher Navoi, "Akhlai muqsini" by Husayn Vaiz Koshifi.

From the mentioned works, it is possible to come to a general conclusion that if the child is the happiness of the parents, education is the child's today, tomorrow and future. That is why education is a social phenomenon. Education has existed since the beginning of human society. After all, in order for a person to be the most perfect breed on earth, he must first be educated. There is a saying among our people that "an educator must first of all be educated". Mutafakkir ibn Sina said to the educators, "Whatever advice you give to someone, that is, first of all, do it yourself." It is the duty of all of us to use the opinions, advice, and wisdom of thinkers in raising children, expanding and enriching their spiritual worldview, and raising a mature person.

Search results.

Articles 76-80 of the Family, Children and Youth Chapter XIV of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan effective from May 1, 2023 - The family is the main link of society and it is under the protection of society and the state, about marriage, the full development of the state family to create social, economic, legal and other conditions for parents and their substitutes to feed their children until they reach adulthood, their upbringing, education, healthy, full and comprehensive In terms of the fact that it is necessary to take care of the child, motherhood, fatherhood and childhood are protected by the state, and adult children who are able to work are obliged to take care of their parents. It has been legally confirmed that it is important.

The family, which is the cradle of education, is a sacred space that preserves the continuity of every people, nation, ensures the development of national values, gives birth to and educates mentally and physically perfect generation, and raises patriotic defenders of the country. A person receives the first education from the family, love, mother's milk and special alla. Its influence is deeply rooted in human nature and soul. A child's perfection, mentality, kindness, and manners

are formed on the basis of the internal, specific rules established in each family. As the President noted, "It is clear to all of us that every person in our country has the best dreams, goals, and vital interests of every family, first of all, in the form of their children, and they come true." The issue of children's spiritual education is also important. Scientist Safo Okhr, who explained the word spirituality, said: "Spirituality" means the beauty, generosity, nobility, loyalty to one's promise, imagination, learning, wisdom, tolerance, neatness and purity of human behavior. the innocence of the heart, politeness and such pleasant customs are understood", - puts forward the opinion.

Discussions.

In his book "Bizkim, Uzbeklar", Abdukahhor Ibrohimov says: "A person can be enlightened without using the word enlightenment a lot, be enlightened, and be spiritual without using the phrase spirituality abusively. Because these are not in the language - enlightenment - in the mind, spirituality - in the heart." According to the scientist, today's women, along with their activities in the development of the society, instill enlightenment in their minds and spirituality in their hearts, they are a kind mother for children in the family, a beloved wife for their spouse, moreover, they are warm and moderate in the family. it is also important to remember that they are creative and sweet mistresses who can create climate and conditions. "The type of education and the method of instilling it in children are different and mutually necessary. However, the education of kindness, honesty, and truthfulness is the most urgent topic of our day".

In fact, a well-rounded person is a bright prospect for the future of every people and nation! Human qualities that accompany a person for a lifetime - kindness, goodness, creativity, selflessness, loyalty, courage, honesty, and compassion are first formed in the family environment. The family environment prepares the ground for the child to grow up to be moral, polite, honest, hardworking, honest and sincere. Family upbringing plays an important role in the development of a child in the future. For a child, a healthy socio-spiritual environment in the family is a source of spiritual and moral values, traditions, social experience and skills. It develops in the process of education. The essence of education is to train a person for life. Family education has a deep impact on children's mental world, emotions and feelings. The lifestyle of family members often determines the mental mood, imagination and emotions of their children.

At the same time, Abdulla Awlani's "good education for the health and happiness of the child is to keep the body clean, correct the profession from a young age, teach good manners, protect from bad manners", Abdurauf Fitrat's "bringing children to adulthood not only the family is responsible for his upbringing, but the whole society is responsible", as stated in Hadisu Sharif, "no parent can give his child anything more than good education and manners", as the folk wisdom says, " a child is like a blank sheet of paper, and filling it with good writings is the duty of parents and teachers", philosopher George Santayana's "family is one of the masterpieces of nature", Abu Ali ibn Sina's "morality is for everyone It is necessary to understand how many ideas about science and manners are embodied in such sayings, which express the content of the culture of etiquette and the place of the family in the education and upbringing of children.

"It is necessary to raise children in the family in such a way that their desire for happiness never fades, does not fade, but grows blue," said Fitrat. Yes, of course, education plays an important role in human life. Since the child spends most of his time with his mother, some people have formed the attitude of looking at upbringing as the duty of mothers. What about father? How important is the role of fathers in raising children, especially boys? Or is mother's education

enough to make a person a perfect person? Was it possible for the father to support the family financially and financially?

No, of course. According to experts, as the outlook of women and men are fundamentally different, fathers should be more involved in the education of boys.

Because the father's role is very important in the upbringing of a boy and a child in general. A man is the fortress of the house, the bulwark of the family in all good and bad times. If there is a problem in the family, the family members rely on him. Therefore, the role of the father in the upbringing of a boy is incomparable, and he has a number of responsibilities. Children brought up in families where the father is the head develop a positive sense of admiration and respect for the father. This is what keeps him from going beyond the "drawn line", from violating various social norms accepted in our life and, in turn, from being subjected to various social sanctions.

Conclusion.

In life, mother is often a teacher and coach for a girl child, and a father is a teacher for a boy. Raising a boy in a family is a complex and long-lasting special process, which should begin long before the birth of a child. That is, the future parents' health, lineage, outlook, inner and outer world, morals, moral and physical readiness for marriage are important in the upbringing of the future child. Each family member, neighbor, neighborhood, educational institution, community is equally responsible for raising a boy in the family. It is not wrong to say that the role of the father is the most important in this system.

In conclusion, while raising a child in the family and in educational institutions imposes a great sense of responsibility on each of us, first of all, we must remember that the child is the continuation of our life, how hard the thorn in his leg is in the heart of the parents, for the sake of the child. We, the team of parents and pedagogues, should always keep in mind that his behavior and manners should be treated as a first-class issue. From this point of view, in child education, pedagogues should be in close cooperation with family and community, hold regular creative meetings and educational activities on spiritual topics based on a strict plan, disciplined and disciplined based on their initiative and suggestions. It is necessary to pay attention to the development and practical implementation of the measures.

REFERENCES

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. May 1, 2023
2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. December 8, 2016. "Khalk Sozi" newspaper.
3. Safo Open. Issues of independence and upbringing. "Uzbekistan", 1995. p.
4. Ibrohimov A. We, the Uzbeks. "Sharq", T.:2011.
5. Family is the support of spiritual development. Materials of the scientific theoretical conference dedicated to the "Year of the Strong Family". NDPI. 2012.
6. Farmanova Muzayyamkan. Child education in the spiritual heritage of Eastern thinkers. scientific and methodical guide. - Ashkent: "Tasvir publishing house", 2020, 23b.
7. The father is the pillar of the family. Scientific-methodical manual. T.: -2019. Scientific and practical research center "Family" under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 35b.
8. Social information and education portal: www.ziyonet.uz.
9. <https://www.lex.uz> - National database of legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.